

METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. this article gives information about methods of teaching foreign language specifically teaching vocabulary during the process of English.

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The general methodology deals with the study of patterns and features of the process of learning a foreign language, regardless of which foreign language is in question. But knowledge of the general laws of teaching a foreign language is not enough when a teacher is faced with the specific features of a particular foreign language, for example, mastering English verb forms specific only to the English language, cumbersome models of the English language, ways of forming numerals in the English language, etc. Therefore, a private methodology explores the teaching of those linguistic and speech phenomena that are specific to a particular foreign language. With one on the other hand, the methodology studies real objects: a program, textbooks, textbooks, a foreign language teacher, a student, and organizational forms of the educational process: a foreign language lesson, extracurricular work, independent work, etc. On the other hand, these are abstract objects, namely: learning objectives, learning content, learning principles, teaching methods and techniques. Every independent science has its own object of research, its own subject of research and its own terminology, i.e. a set of categories and concepts.

The object of research of the methodology is considered to be the learning process foreign language in general. Consequently, all components of the educational process can be attributed here: The quality of the real educational process in a foreign language is determined by the interrelation of all subjective and objective factors of this process that determine its effectiveness.

So, the object of the study of the methodology of teaching foreign languages are specific forms of manifestation of the educational process: lessons, extracurricular activities, independent work of students, as well as specific forms of activity of teachers and students and the entire arsenal of means of teaching foreign languages. The subject of the methodology research is numerous methodological theories that model the process of teaching foreign languages. The subject of the methodology is

also the goals and content of training, principles of training, teaching methods and methodological techniques. The subject of the methodology is also language as a means of communication. The methodology of teaching foreign languages theoretically substantiates, experimentally verifies and practically implements the model (system) of language teaching.

Among the private methods of teaching school subjects, an obvious boundary lies between subjects whose purpose of teaching is the assimilation of knowledge: these are literature, history, physics, biology, etc., and subjects that require the formation of skills and abilities: drawing, physical education, music and work in all its manifestations. The mathematical cycle of disciplines stands apart, in which the transfer of knowledge is aimed at the formation of abstract thinking. In this series, only teaching foreign languages turns out to be an “omnivorous” subject. Its purpose is to acquire knowledge about the language and culture of the people, and the formation of speech skills and abilities, and the development of abstract thinking in the course of combining new language material in unfamiliar communication situations. Hence the long search for a niche for the methodology of teaching foreign languages, the formation of which as a science has been carried out for a number of decades. During this period, the question of the status of this scientific discipline was the most controversial. Thus, L.V. Shcherba noted that the methodology is applied linguistics, and B.V. Belyaev considered the methodology to be applied psychology. I.V. Rakhmanov also questioned the independent scientific status of the methodology [4]. The modern point of view on methodology as a theory of teaching a foreign language boils down to the statement that methodology is an independent science with its own specifics and identity, with its own object of research, subject of research and terminology. Methodics of teaching a foreign language as an independent discipline it begins to take shape only at the turn of the 18th and 19th centuries. Until that time, the issues of foreign language methodology were dealt with exclusively by representatives of general pedagogy. The first attempts to theoretically substantiate the methods of learning new foreign languages are found in the works of the French teacher Jacot (1822), in the works of the Russian teacher K.D. Ushinsky, the Russian methodologist Orbinsky [5], etc. In the second half of the 19th century, the methodology was finally formed into an independent scientific discipline.

In total, it is based on the “image of language” that exists in linguistics at each specific period of its development [6]. So, since the beginning of the 1950s, the idea of consistency has acquired a special influence in linguistics, which for many decades determined a level-based learning model that repeats the structure of the

language and its image. Therefore, until the 1960s, the methodology of teaching foreign languages focused on the issues of mastering language material, despite the fact that students' mastery of a foreign language as a means of oral and written communication was declared as practical learning tasks.

Since the mid-1960s, in linguistics, along with the study of the language system, the research of speech, which is understood as the implementation of the language system in specific acts of communication, has been developing more and more consistently.

Linguists draw a strict distinction between language competence and language use. The methodology, in turn, addresses the problem of not only the assimilation of linguistic means and the rules of their use in speech, but also their automated use in acts of communication, that is, the problem of teaching speech activity.

Since the 1970s, linguistics has turned to the social and functional aspects of language analysis. This means that the sphere of interests of linguists includes the analysis of the mechanism of using language for various purposes arising in the course of social interaction. During this period, linguistic research receives a pronounced pragmatic orientation, while the main task is not to study the structure of language, but its functioning - A new paradigm for analyzing speech communication is formed primarily by the theory of speech activity and the theory of speech acts. The theory of speech activity, which emerged at the turn of the 1970s, allowed us to reveal the essence of speech communication in the context of a social situation in which the communicants interact with each other. The pronounced pragmatic orientation of linguistic research in the 1970s and 1980s manifested itself in the general conceptual position of methodology as a science and in the technology of teaching foreign languages. Methodological approaches have acquired a pronounced communicative character. This led to a radical a turn to natural communication in the process of language learning, which is aimed at the formation of communicative competence taking into account situational and personal factors. By the early 1980s, methodological science had accumulated a rich arsenal of effective teaching methods aimed not only at developing students' skills to practically use the language, but also at the general development and education of students. It should be noted that modern methodological science is showing increasing interest in the extralinguistic conditions and circumstances of foreign language communication, to the personality of the subjects involved in communication, their knowledge of the world. This determines the cultural orientation of the modern methodology. That is why the learning process in a foreign

language should be presented as a process of transferring linguistic and cultural experience.

Knowledge of the methodological patterns of teaching a foreign language forms the basis of the teacher's professional and methodological skills. This means that a teacher can achieve high-quality results in his professional activity if he is methodically literate and well knows how to teach a foreign language in a specific learning environment. Ignorance of the theoretical and applied foundations of teaching a foreign language puts the teacher in conditions when he is forced to go through trial and error and often choose not the shortest and most effective way to the planned result. But it must also be borne in mind that knowledge alone is not enough. It is very important to have the ability and desire to use this knowledge rationally and effectively in teaching practice, to transform the mastered methodological techniques and methods of work on the basis of this knowledge and transfer them to new learning conditions.

The methodology of teaching foreign languages, due to its specificity, is subject to numerous dangers associated with unreasonable hobbies, ignoring important factors that determine the solution of any methodological issue. There is nowhere so easy and unpunished to manifest pseudovatorship as in teaching a foreign language, especially after more than half a century of ignoring the importance of this the subject. In these conditions, such personalities as T.I. Arbekova, A.A. Leontiev, O.V. Afanyaseva, N.V. Beregovaya, G.Y. Bogdanovich, G.V. Rogova and N.D. Galskova acquire special importance for our science.

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